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Comparative study of Quantum Mechanical Behaviour in the light of Jain Philosophy

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1. Introduction

When philosophical ideas associated with science are dragged into another field, they are usually completely distorted. Therefore we shall confine our remarks as much as possible to some part of Jain philosophy and as well as material aspect and behaviour regarding quantum physics itself. Quantum Physics sometimes dealing with the behaviour of matter and light on the atomic and sub-atomic scale. It attempts to describe and account for the properties of molecules and atoms and their constituents. The most interesting aspect is the idea of the wave-particle duality, Niels Bohr's complementarity principle, uncertainty principle etc. On the other hand, the Jaina philosophy of *anekāntavāda*, particularly *syādvāda* points out the similarity with modern science like Niels Bohr's Principle of complementarity, uncertainty principle. In Jain philosophy, matter has been analysed on the basis of its conception as a permanent substance possessing infinite qualities and modes with unique notions about it as physical science. In this context it would be studied comparatively between some of quantum mechanical aspect and Jaina philosophy. To begin with the concept of matter by throwing light on Jaina conception of Reality- *Dravya* (substance), *guṇa* (quality) and *pariyāya* (mode) and

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their inter relation has been discussed. *Dravya* has been conceived by the Jainas as a universal principle of Reality from the aspect of generality, while its particular characteristic are *Jivadravya* (living substance) and *Ajivadravya* (non-living substance). It is to be noted that *Jivadravya* and *Ajivadravya* of Jain philosophy do not form any two substance-doctrine, representing the world of animated substances and non-animated substances as independent and self-contained system.

2. Concept of matter in philosophical view

According to Jain philosophy '*Pudgala*' represents the elements of matter. Gramatically, the samskrita term '*Pudgala*' is very sound and consists of two words- *pud* and *gala* connoting the two important qualities of matter – association (*pud*-) and dissociation (*gala*). Although, in earlier, the scientists are like to use two different terms for *Pudgala* of Jainas – matter and energy separately. But after Einstein (*The Theory of Relativity*) both the terms have been merged in scientific world. This is very significant according to Jaina philosophy. Although the scientists define matter with three common properties-

- (i) It should occupy space or it should have a volume or form.
- (ii) It should have a weight.
- (iii) It should be subject to our experience or knowledge.

The Jainas counter only (i) and (ii) as common property of matter, though their concept of *Agurulaghutva* – neither-heavy nor-light connotes the idea of weight indirectly.

Actually, the nine substance of the Vedic philosophy like Earth, Water, Fire, Air, space, time, direction soul and mind can be reduced to six substances of Jain philosophy which are constituents of the universe. They are *Jiva* (soul), *Dharma* (principle of motion), *Adharma* (principle of rest), *Ākāśa* (space) *Pudgala* (matter) and *Kāla* (time). So, *Pudgala* is one of the six *Dravya* (substance) that fabricate

the world we live in. Jaina philosophy says that the *Pudgala* is permanent substance which the material universe is constituted, undergoing changes by the process of integration and disintegration. The individual unit of *Pudgala* is the material from which all is made called *Paramāṇu* (atom).

3. Jaina Philosophy and Atom (*Paramāṇu*)

A *Paramāṇu* represents smallest homogeneous part of any substance. Jaina philosophy maintains that *Paramāṇu* is both cause (*Karma*) and effect (*Kārya*) of the material world from the standpoint transformation which takes place elements of matter, due to external and internal causes. The Jaina conception of *Paramāṇu* as cause and effect is parallel to the conception of energy and consequence of energy of the physical science. According to the Jainas, *Paramāṇu* is *ekānta* (discrete) and beginningless. It is one of class like the energy of matter of the physical science. According to Jain philosophy all *Sukṣma Paramāṇu* are *abhedyā* (impassable or impenetrable), *acchedyā* (uncuttable), *avibhājyā* (indivisible), *adāhya* (incombustible) and *agrāhya* (non-receivable). Most of properties are assumed in physical science in heat and thermodynamics. The colour, taste, smell and touch exist as equal in each and every *paramāṇu* and can change into any form according to cause. The Jaina philosophy explain all gross and fine material creations (products) on the basis of the capacity of transformation of *paramāṇus* and their combination and dissociation just as the *Sāṃkhya* accounts for the production of multiforms of the gross and fine material entities of the universe on the ground of differentiated combination of *guṇas* (qualities).

Sattva (essence), *Rajas* (energy) and *Tamas* (inertia or mass) from *Prakṛti* one-primordial matter and its capacity of transformation. In study of atomism, Jain philosophy is the advocate of the atomic theory like the *Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika*. From the point of view of consequence makes it explain that *paramāṇu-pudgala* is not *jīva* (soul) but *ājīva* (non-soul) i.e, soul can not exist in *paramāṇu* but soul and *paramāṇu* can exist together is one space-point.

Wave particle duality

Wave–particle duality is the concept in quantum mechanics that every particle or quantum entity may be described as either a particle or a wave. It expresses the inability of the classical concepts “particle” or “wave” to fully describe the behaviour of quantum-scale objects. According to Jaina philosophy, particularly in *syādvāda*, every fact of reality leads to seven ways or modes of description. These are the combinations of affirmation, negation, and inexpressibility – namely, (1) Existence, (2) Nonexistence, (3) Occurrence of existence and Nonexistence, (4) Inexpressibility or Indeterminateness, (5) Inexpressibility as qualified by existence, (6) In expressibility as qualified by Nonexistence. The fourth mode i.e, the inexpressibility known as *avyaktavya* is the key element of the *syādvāda* dialectic. This is especially well brought out by the foregoing discussion of the wave–particle duality. When one uses terms like ‘particle’ or ‘waves’, one must use them to mean what they usually describe in physics. The quantum description involves an unobserved state of the electron which is neither corpuscular nor wave like. The Jaina position on *avyaktavyam* tells that indescribable by ordinary language.

Quantum mechanical aspect

In wave particle duality, a particle behaves in different ways at different times. This is clear from the famous two-slit experiment which is the backbone of quantum mechanics and wave–particle duality. *Anekānta vāda* not only explains seemingly contradictory propositions in daily life, philosophy, macroworld, mental exercises and in spiritual domain, it also brought in the concept of *Avyakta* or inexpressibility of certain states. Questions which can not be answered in affirmative or negative, like the existence of soul, could be dealt with in the framework of *Anekānt vāda*. It is, it is not; it is and yet it is not, it can not be expressed and so on. This concept is common to Quantum behavior.

Anekānta vāda is not simply a multiview perception theory. It is not a limitation of consciousness that it has limited capability of perception of the physical world. Thus it is not the consequence of

not being able to look at an object from different perspectives but that the object can not be known from all the perspectives. *Anekāntavāda* is as fundamental as the Uncertainty Principle, which states that some dynamical variables like position (Δx) and momentum (Δp) of a particle can not be simultaneously measured with arbitrarily high precision, not because of instrumental limitations but because of inherent behavior of nature. Therefore, there is an inherent uncertainty involved in the concept of an unobserved quantum mechanical state (a potentiality) vis-à-vis the observable outcomes. The relevance to quantum mechanics of the *Syādvāda* concept of *Avaktavyam* to mean indeterminacy with the consequent implications for probability.

Thus, in the physical world, as in philosophy, things or ideas have plurality of attributes and these can be apparently contradictory or conflicting. *Anekāntvāda* successfully harmonises or accommodates such views and completes the description of physical reality. But when we talk of manyfoldedness, the question obviously arises, how many. Certainly more than one, but can it be infinite? *saptbhangī* or sevenfoldedness is a corollary of *Anekāntavāda*. This has been very clearly explained by D.S. Kothari in his essay on “*Complementarity Principle and Eastern Philosophy*”. According to the principle of *Saptabhangī* reality can be described in seven ways i.e. it exists, it does not exist, it exists and yet it does not exist, indeterminable, its existence is indeterminable, its non existence is indeterminable and its existence as well as non existence is indeterminable or inexpressible. *Saptabhangī* has been explained very succinctly by Kothari in a quantum mechanical way by taking the example of a particle in a box which is divided by a partition with a hole into two compartments. Because of the particle-wave duality, the particle can be in compartment A, or in compartment B, In A and still not in A, In B and still not in B, not in A and B, in A as well as in B and in an indeterminate state (*avyakta*). The same solutions emerge from the considerations of quantum mechanics as has been shown mathematically by taking wave functions.

Conclusion

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Environmental degradation and its impact on Jainism

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Abstract

Jainism is one of the most significant, heterodox and oldest religions, not only in India but also in the world which proposed the principles of ecology and conservation of environment. The Jainism considers that we must have an awareness of the holy tie between human being and environment which is necessary for our planet and its health as well as the survival of flora and fauna. Everything that surrounds us collectively forms the environment. The air, the soil, the water, the rivers, the mountains, the plants, the animals, in short, all living and non-living things around, comprises the environment, which has influenced and shaped lives since the time immemorial. The environment constitutes a life support system for all beings. Through a process of natural selection and elimination, it is the environment that has directed the evolution of the biosphere, as it exists today. Therefore, we must not deprive our mother earth from its resources with misusing, draining and polluting it.

Introduction

There is a Jain parable that demonstrates that even animals, which are on a lower level of evolution than man, exhibit qualities of compassion for fellow beings and concern for environment. Man, despite his superior brain, is lacking in wisdom exhibited by animals. However, primitive man did not look upon nature with indifference and arrogance. That is a modern

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It is interesting to compare Jaina philosophy with classical physics as well as quantum physics. Both swear by objectivity, rationality and empiricism. However unlike quantum physics, Jaina Philosophy contains transcendental topic such as rebirth and doctrine of *karma*. This is exactly why Jaina *anekānta* cannot be called hard science. Although, *Anekānta* is a broad philosophy. *Syādvāda* has a social dimension. This philosophy leads one to tolerance and ahimsa or non-violence. Apart from its philosophical and ethical values and in spite of its different historical and cultural moorings, *Syādvāda* had rich scientific potential which, however, remained unrealized for thousands of years. It was well ahead of its time in this respect.

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